

Statistics: bayesvl and BMF analytics

This page provides a quick glance at official publications that use either the bayesvl package in R [1] or the BMF analytics [2] (or both). The data will tell a bit about the research community's efforts made over time and the growth of the bayesvl/BMF analytics community.

Aggregates:

Overall, the bayesvl R package was downloaded 24,453 times from May 24, 2019, to May 09, 2025 ([downloads](#) [222/month](#)).

In total, 73 publications have been published using either the bayesvl or BMF analytics.

The above 73 publications have been written by 140 authors, coming from 177 universities/research institutions, representing 16 countries/territories.

Annual/cumulative statistics:

Year	Number of publications	Cumulative number of publications	Cumulative number of authors	Cumulative number of institutions	Cumulative number of countries
2025	4	73	140	177	16
2024	27	69	133	162	16
2023	14	42	66	109	12
2022	7	28	49	82	7
2021	15	21	41	65	5
2020	4	6	25	41	4
2019	2	2	14	11	3

(*) Note: The hyperlink provided in each cell in the first column will lead to a page that enumerates all the papers published in the corresponding year.

References

- [1] La VP, Vuong QH. (2019). bayesvl: Visually Learning the Graphical Structure of Bayesian Networks and Performing MCMC with 'Stan'. The Comprehensive R Archive Network. <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/bayesvl/index.html>
- [2] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH, La VP. (2022). The mindsponge and BMF analytics for innovative thinking in social sciences and humanities. Walter de Gruyter GmbH. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/8367405102/>